

The past, present and future contributions of small-scale and local food supply systems to Nigeria's food security: a critical appraisal

Adewale M. Ogunmodede

Department of Sustainable Agriculture and Food Security,
School of Agriculture, Food and Environment,
Royal Agricultural University, Cirencester, GL7 6JS, United Kingdom.
Email: adewale.ogunmodede@student.rau.ac.uk

Abstract

Despite the widely acclaimed contributions of oil to Nigeria's growth, agriculture remains a major backbone of the economy, although its drive toward food security and sufficiency has waned over-time as there is a high rate of food importation to meet production's deficit. The successes of Nigerian Agriculture are attributed to small-scale farmers who are about 80% of the driver for local food production and supply. Various policies have been formulated to tackle the challenges faced by agriculture, ranging from inadequate funding, inadequate storage facilities, migration, poor roads, etc but all have failed to fully end these problems. Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA) which came up in 2011 only reduced importation to some extent. It is hoped that the new policy, Agricultural Promotion will correct the lapses of ATA. For the smallholders to contribute sustainably to food security, there is a need for the government to put in place mechanisms that incorporates both the farmers and women into active participation in policy formulations.

Keywords: rural development; food security; local foods; production; poverty reduction; women empowerment; sustainability

1.0 Introduction

Being the most populous black state in the world, 47% of West Africa's population are Nigerians (World Bank, 2012); with currently estimated people of about 200 million occupying land size above 92 million ha but only 82 million ha is available for agricultural production (PWC, 2017). Despite Nigeria having the continent's largest natural gas reserves and one of the biggest oil exporters, Agriculture is still the mainstay of the economy where it employs about 2/3rd of its labour force and accounts for 40% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (IFAD, 2012).

Fig 1: Trends in Projection of Nigeria's population.

Source: PwC (2019)

From history, Nigerian Agriculture still sustains the economy despite the discovery of oil where it employs about 2/3rd of its labour force and contributes 40% to the GDP. The country suffers from food deficit and relies on food importation to feed its people despite being the world's largest producer of cassava, beans and yam (FAO, 2019; IFAD, 2012). Of the estimated 82million ha cultivable land, only 32 million hectares are farmed; generating export earnings of about US\$1.4Billion which amounts to contributing 24.4% to the GDP. This resulted in importing food products worth US\$5.3billion to meet the food deficit (AGRA, 2017; PWC, 2017).

Smallholders are responsible for most food produced in Nigeria, accounting for about 80% of the farmers. Small-scale farms despite being less than 10 ha per farmers still play a key role in providing about 99% and 98% of total local food supply and consumption in Nigeria (Mgbenka & Mbah, 2016). These rural farmers operate on a subsistence level whose production is based on small plots with varying seasonal rainfall. Inadequate infrastructures such as good roads, storage facilities, high inputs cost, illiteracy, land-tenure and other social amenities have reduced their productivity and increased poverty incidence among the rural people (IFAD, 2012). Increases in population pressures on limited resources, deforestation, overgrazing and over-farming are threatening our local food supply. While erosion is a major challenge facing Southern Nigeria, the North is faced with constant drought which has affected food production. Among the crops grown by the farmers are maize, rice, millet, cocoa, cassava, cashew and sorghum; while animals include cattle, pigs, goats, poultry birds and camels.

1.1 Local Food supply and Small-Scale Farming in Nigeria: contributions from past to present.

Before the discovery of oil, Nigeria's food export, productivity and performance were driven by small-scale farmers who ensured that their productions met the local demands ensuring food security, developing

agro-allied industries through the supply of raw materials and supporting the livelihood of about 70% of the population. Their activities then according to Ahungwa, Haruna, & Abdusalam (2014) made Nigeria be the world’s largest producer of cassava, cocoa, oil palm, rubber, peanuts and cotton accounting for 67% of the GDP and generating over 62% in foreign earning in 1965. Northern Nigeria was reputed for its towering groundnut pyramids which were cultivated by the smallholders. The discovery of oil in the 1970s however made agriculture to be neglected, thereby making petroleum to be the major contributor to the

GDP. The figures contributed by agriculture in the 1960s can be seen to be higher than the average of 21% contributed between 2011 to 2017 according to Fig. 2 below.

Fig 2: Contributions of agriculture and import bills from 2008-2018 Source: PwC (2019)

Crops mostly are grown by farmers to combat hunger and food insecurity are maize, cassava, yam, millets and sorghum (Steve Wiggins, 2009). According to Eigege & Cooke (2016), the activities of these farmers made Nigeria food secured thereby selling off excess produce to the international market leading to foreign exchange generation. But by the 1970s during the oil boom period, there was a mass exodus of rural dwellers to the urban centre on look-out for white-collar jobs thereby neglecting agriculture, signalling massive rural-urban migration. Population increase and unfavourable government policies in food prices reduction crippled the local food supply as there was no motivation for farmers to continue in production. Igbokwe (1983) noted that about a 250% increase in importation between 1972 and 1980 crippled the local food supply and export supply as the agricultural production per capita reduced by almost 35%. Nigeria food imports such as rice, wheat and sugar in 2013 amounted to \$11 billion which has drained the economy with the falling prices of oil and recession. The table below shows the trend analysis of exportation to importation from 2013-2016 in relation to local food supply.

Table 1: Nigeria's Agricultural Importation and Exportation Trends from 2013-2016

Agricultural Production	2013	2014	2015	2016
Rice	4,823,330 MT	6,002,831 MT	6,256,228 MT	6,070,813 MT
Wheat	80,000 MT	70,000 MT	60,000 MT	60,000 MT
Maize	8,422,670 MT	10,058,968 MT	10,562,050 MT	10,414,012 MT
Soybean	517,960 MT	623,815 MT	588,523 MT	588,201 MT
Agricultural Exports				
Rice	144.00 MT	681.00 MT	427.00 MT	124.00 MT
Wheat	100.00 MT	3,101 MT	6.00 MT	21.00 MT
Maize	7,530 MT	10,488 MT	6,185 MT	3,161 MT
Soybean	8,800 MT	9,000 MT	9,000 MT	9,000 MT
Agricultural Imports				
Rice	1,882,759 MT	2,187,419 MT	2,455,202 MT	2,187,370 MT
Wheat	3,971,861 MT	4,039,669 MT	4,067,155 MT	4,358,863 MT
Maize	550.00 MT	812.00 MT	1,000.00 MT	1,200 MT
Soybean	9.00 MT	9.00 MT	5,721 MT	12,757 MT

Source: (Food security Portal, n.d.)

The country's share of global production and export has dwindled over the years especially that of cocoa, groundnuts and oil-palm due to low technological adoption. Poverty, degradation and migration have forced them to continue to produce on a small scale. Despite being one of the world's largest producers of cassava, oil palm, peanut and cocoa, their yield is still falling below the average of other countries. This could be ascribed to the use of improved inputs and technology which other countries are fully utilizing to improve their yield, but which Nigeria is yet to tap fully into (PWC, 2017). The figures below show the agricultural yield and production of selected crops.

Fig 3: Agricultural yield and production of selected crops

Source: PWC (2017); FAO (2019).

Problems affecting local food supply chains and market

Problems are not only facing the production sector, but a lot are also bedevilling the supply chains market. This review will centre its analysis on sub-sectors which are of government priority in revamping the agricultural sector. The problems facing the agricultural sector in Nigeria is summarized by the figure below.

Fig 4: Showing problems facing Agriculture and food supply in Nigeria Source: PwC (2019).

It is estimated that Cocoa is grown in 14 states in Nigeria by 30,000 subsistence farmers. Small and medium-scale farmers, cooperatives, Local buying agents, merchants and processors including manufacturing firms are the main actors in the cocoa value chain. It is known all over the world that processing of cocoa into its derivatives have the potential to increase farmers income and generate substantial foreign exchange, but it is disheartening to discover that in Nigeria, only 30% of the beans are processed with the rest being exported. In 2016, Nigeria generated \$144 million from cocoa beans export. The figure below shows cocoa production in four countries.

Table 2: Top World Cocoa producing countries statistics.

Country	Production of cocoa beans (in '000 tonnes)	Cocoa export -beans & derivatives (in '000 tonnes)	Cocoa exports in value (in million US\$)
Ivory Coast	1,434.0	1,022.7	2,933.0
Ghana	858.7	546.6	1,447.0
Indonesia	728.4	384.8	1,099.7
Nigeria	248.0	222.8	564.0

Source: PWC (2017).

Various researches show that inadequate farm inputs, high incidence of pests, diseases and extension workers including ageing of cocoa trees are responsible for the reduction in yield of Cocoa in Nigeria (PWC, 2017).

Cattle population in Nigeria is estimated to be 20 million with the about 12 million pastoralists controlling 95% of the total dairy output. Nigeria’s milk production is the lowest in the world with 0.6 million tonnes (0.6-2.5 litres per animal/day) as compared to Africa’s 0.9 million tonnes and the world’s average of 6.6 million tonnes. This problem can be attributed to the lower yield of 2,458 hg/Animal compared to Asia’s 31,835hg/Animal. Research shows evidence of wastage due to lack of storage facilities, as about 80% of fresh milk is sold to the consumers, 15% to local processors (fura, wara and nunu) while 5% is sold to the Dairy firms with only 3% accessible, which is far less than the 10% required leading to the importation of Milk. Other notable problems are inadequate access to credit, lack of improved breeds, water and feed shortage, small and scattered collection centre and the pastoralist system of farming (UNDP, 2013; Nigeria

Dairy Enterprise Initiative Program, 2007). Littering of the value chains with middlemen and weak linkages has led to the slower growth of the chains. Similarly, the rate of insecurity fuelled by ethnic, religious and herdsmen-farmers crises is affecting workers, business and agricultural production.

Also, despite the yearly production of about 600,000MT of fishery resources by small scale farmers, we are still the largest importer of frozen fish in Africa requiring about 2.6 million MT yearly. Post-harvest losses, transportation problems, inadequate infrastructures and poor regulation is hampering the growth of the fishery industry (UNDP, 2013).

Table 3: Gap estimates in food demand and local food supply of Nigeria (2016)

CROP	DEMAND (TONS)	SUPPLY (TONS)	Source of local supply
Rice	6.3million	2.3million	Small scale
Wheat	4.7million	0.06million	Small scale
Maize/corn	7.5million	7.0million	Small scale
Soy Bean	0.75million	0.6million	Small scale
Tomato	2.2million	0.8million	Small scale
Yam	39million	37million	Small scale
Oil palm	8.0million	4.5million	Small scale
Cocoa	3.6million	0.25million	Small scale
Cotton	0.7million	0.2million	Small scale
Sorghum	7.0million	6.2million	Small scale
Fish	2.7million	0.8million	Small scale
Milk/dairy	2.0million	0.6million	Small scale
Chicken	200million birds	140million	Small scale

Source: FMARD (2016).

Fig 5: Local demand-supply gap of key agricultural products

Source: FMARD (2016); PWC (2017).

2.0 Agricultural and Food Security Policies in Nigeria: Past and Current

2.1 Contributions of Nigeria's past Agricultural and Food Security Policies on small-scale farming and local food supply

In stemming the tide of agricultural problems in Nigeria, different approaches comprising labour demand, labour supply and labour market interventions had been initiated by the government in the past. However, the impact has been minimal. This, of course, indicates the extent to which these initiatives and interventions had been ineffective in reducing poverty and food insecurity. Although, these programmes had focused on self-sufficiency and improvement in rural livelihood towards achieving food production sufficiency and security; corruption and inconsistency in policies had made most of these interventions to have little impacts on the lives of the farmers. A detailed summary of various government agricultural policies and programmes from 1960-2001 is shown by the table below.

Table 4: Showing the various Nigerian Agricultural and Food Policies (1960-2001)

Year	Policy	Main objective	Disposition towards small-scale farming
Colonial Era	Undocumented but seems to be the continuation of British Industrial Revolution Policy during colonization	Cash crops export promotion	This Supports the exportation of Cash crops to cater for British industrial needs and unfavourable of small-scale farmers.
Before Civil war	National Accelerated Food Production Program (NAFPP)	Targeted to increase domestic production for local consumption and export earnings for GDP	Focused on commercial farms to achieve goal.
1976	Operation Feed the Nation (OFN)	Enlarge National Welfare by reducing food prices and level of importation	Diversion of loans to non-farmers.
1980	Green Revolution	Improve agricultural productivity by Increasing domestic production for local consumption and improving on export crops through technology adoption.	Loans were diverted from small scale farmers to larger scale farmers.
1983	Back to Land	Self-sufficiency in food production	This supported small scale farming but failed shortly due to insufficient input and technology deficiencies.
1985	Directorate for Foods, Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI)	Reducing rural-urban migration and poverty	Inconsistency in policy and inadequate involvement of rural farmers.
1999	Commercial Agricultural Development Program (CADP)	Developing the tripod of Production, Processing and Storage.	This embraced small-scale farming by introducing Guaranteed Minimum Price to stabilize market price for smallholders, innovation of farmers' market to create market access, establishment of agro-input centres for smallholders etc. Impact not stated but obviously, it has not solved the problems of the farmers as new policy was

2001	The New Nigeria Agricultural Policy	Self-sufficiency in basic food supply and attainment of food security by introducing improved seeds and recognition of the potentials of small-scale farmers as the main food producers in the country. Creating an enabling environment for the policy to thrive.	A whole part of the policy was in favour of the smallholders. However, there was no literature capturing the evaluation after expiration of the policy. The introduction of the ATA shows that the problems are still in existence and there is still much more to be achieved
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2.2 Contributions of Nigeria's present Agricultural and Food Security Policies on small-scale farming and local food supply.

2.2.1 Agricultural Transformation Agenda (2011- 2015)

Having to understudy the factors contributing to the past agricultural policies failures, the government of President Jonathan came up with a unique agenda for the agricultural sector, called the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA). FMARD envisioned ATA to accelerate nutritional and food security provides employment and position Nigeria as a force in the international market thereby ensuring a better livelihood for smallholders. ATA focused on commodities such as Cassava, sorghum, rice; including aquaculture, livestock and horticulture. ATA objective is based on import substitution whereby locally produced crops (cassava) are substituted for imported ones (wheat) in making bread and so on. This is to ensure encouraging the smallholders into continuous production with the assurance of available market for both the farmers and the industries thereby discouraging importation. Despite this innovative idea, Nigeria still relies heavily on food importation to meet domestic demand. The table below summaries ATA's programme.

Table 5: Summary of ATA achievements and shortcomings

Area	Successes	Failures
Local Food Production	New high yielding crop varieties introduced. Establishment of Federal Govt. Dept. of Agricultural Extension. Increases in local food production and supply.	Inadequate input supplies hampered the growth in food production. Gender inequality in terms of beneficiaries.
Local Market Access	Re-establishment of some commodity marketing boards	Illegal importation of food still thriving. Slow reduction in post-harvest losses.
Infrastructural Development	Establishment of Staple crop processing zones (SCPZ) for industrial growth. Franchise of Federal warehouses assets	Free trade and crop processing zones failed to live up to expectations. Slower growth in infrastructural development.
Input Supply	Increased farmers access to subsidized inputs e.g fertilizer and seeds. E-wallet provision and registration of smallholders thereby increasing their access to subsidies. About 10.5 million accounts were opened for farmers under GES. About 14 million farmers benefitted from the GES subsidies from 2011-2015.	Inadequate supplies of inputs as there is huge gap between demand and supply of seeds (about 300,000MT). Leakage problems from farmers registration, input supply to distribution logistics. Increase in indebtedness to banks due to exit from GES focus.
Credit Financing	Creation of special funds to support farmers e.g. N10billion Cassava fund. Establishment of Nigeria Incentive-based Risk Sharing system for Agricultural Lending (NIRSAL). Increased funding for Bank of Agriculture. Partnerships with Banks to boost lending to Agriculture and GES from 1% to 6%.	Unpaid GES loans (N39B) slowed down lending to farmers. Non-actualization of both foreign and domestic investors commitments funding. NIRSAL credit guarantee rules affected market for agriculture financing.

Source: FMARD (2016)

2.2.2 Agricultural Promotion Policy 2016-2020.

Due to the problems encountered by the ATA, the government saw a need to come up with a new policy called **Agricultural Promotion Policy (APP)**, 2016-2020. The focus of the APP is to combat the menace of inefficiency in the availability of local food supply and production. To generate foreign exchange, APP aims to “restart the clock” by stabilizing export crops production through a public-private partnership, commercializing agriculture, eradicate bottlenecks and corruptions in the transfer of funds and inputs to farmers, linking the producers directly to the market and supporting the farmers by strengthening the supply chains through market linkages. The implementation of this policy is almost ending and so far, it has focused the small-scale farmers. The APP has prioritized some produce to ensure food security at both local and international markets. Some of them are cassava, maize, rice, soybeans, cocoa, oil palm, cowpea and animal products. Lack of local processing and agricultural technology at the small-scale level is a major problem since fabricators have lower capacity.

3.0 Policy Implications for Small-scale farming and Local food supply

This review has been able to establish the pivotal roles played by the small-scale farmers in ensuring food security in Nigeria and beyond like that of Asia green revolutions. Evidence from this review shows that agricultural development is a pre-condition for industrialization and the imminent underdevelopment of

Nigeria is as a result of neglect of the agricultural sector and the smallholders by the various governments leading to low food production and increase in importation. Furthermore, various past policies have failed in changing the fortune of this sector as they do not focus on the small-scale farmers. Policy instruments have been unstable in Nigeria due to the high rate of programmes turnover. To revamp this sector, there is a need for a paradigm shift in policy formulation. This review suggests a “*two-edged sword*” approach to integrating SSF into Nigeria’s agricultural development. This approach combines two methodologies; “*Gender equality*” (GE) and “*Community Driven Development*” (CDD).

Research has shown that about 60% of Nigeria’s smallholders are women. Women are regarded as a change agent and breadwinner of many homes but are constrained by disparities in resource-control, decision making, education and benefiting equally from various government programmes. Past policies such as OFN and ATA have not focused fully on women in agriculture whereas without considering the contributions of smallholder women, real agricultural development cannot occur. Therefore, there is a need for policy shift acknowledging women’s role in community and agricultural development and focusing on helping them to overcome challenges towards more contribution to this sector.

With CCD, agricultural policies will revolve around the local people. This new policy should focus on meeting the need of the people and not just a jamboree. This can be achieved if the policymakers go to the smallholders as learners to understand them. This is to enable the smallholders to have a sense of belonging by doing their investigations themselves and plan the programmes with the policymakers. Failures of past policies have been attributed to not carrying the people along by using a **Top-bottom** instead of a **Bottom-up approach**. CCD enables the people to share their knowledge by exposing their local knowledge through interaction thereby planning the outcome of the programme themselves. Similarly, there is a need for a policy that strengthens land administration system that establishes the smallholder’s legal ownership of their community land in-order to be useful as collateral for credit acquisitions thereby solving the problem of access to credit. This paradigm approach aims at correcting past policies failures and building on their successes through complementing the ATA and APP.

4.0 *Policy Implementation Strategies for Small-scale farming and Local food supply*

- Future government programmes must stipulate the minimum percentage of women beneficiaries.
- To solve land administration problems, the government should put in place efficient customary laws and court.
- Setting up of Monitoring and Evaluation officers to monitor the policy implementation. This will ensure the aims of the programmes are not derailed, checks and balances are ensured to guards against corruption and misappropriation of funds and inputs.
- To strengthen the local food supply, there is a need for an efficient marketing system that incorporates a public-private partnership. This is to encourage production expansion and stimulates value chains investments by removing all bottlenecks.
- To ensure agricultural sustainability, research institutions must be well funded towards researching into improved seeds and chemicals.
- Strengthening of Extension support services to ensure CCD approach functions optimally. Agents should get information, training, inputs and technology transfer to farmers on time.
- Decentralizing National food policy model into regional one like that of Cuba.

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